

Perceived Impact of Geogebra Technology on Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Students' Creativity and Innovation in Geometric Learning amidst Economic Hardship

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This study examined the perceived impact of Geogebra technology on Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic students' creativity and innovation in geometric learning amidst economic hardship. A descriptive survey design was employed with 198 N. D students as a sample, and data were collected using a four-point Likert scale questionnaire (PIGCI). Results analyzed with mean and standard deviation revealed that Geogebra enhanced creativity by enabling students to generate diverse ideas, approach problems from multiple perspectives, and refine unique solutions. It also fostered innovation, as students discovered new methods, experimented with untested ideas, and developed original designs or improved existing approaches. Overall, findings showed that students perceived Geogebra to have a high impact, exceeding the established criterion mean of 2.5. The study concludes that Geogebra, as a cost-effective open-source tool, supports creative and innovative learning despite economic challenges. It recommends wider integration of Geogebra in teaching geometry across Nigerian higher institutions.

Keywords
GeoGebra,
creativity,
innovation,
geometric
learning,
economic
hardship

Introduction

Polytechnic education in Nigeria equips students with thoughtful applied skills, reinforced by strong mathematical foundations, especially in geometry. Spatial reasoning, geometric construction, and problem-solving are central to fields like engineering drawing, surveying, design technology, and construction. However, many students struggle with these competencies due to traditional teaching methods that rely heavily on static diagrams and rote memorization, rather than interactive exploration and conceptual discovery. Meanwhile, economic hardship further affects student learning by limiting access to modern instructional resources, maintenance of laboratories, and availability of real-world visual aids, thereby reducing opportunities for creativity and innovation in the mathematics classroom. Digital active mathematics tools provide a compelling solution to these challenges.

Geogebra is an open-source, interactive software integrating geometry, algebra, and graphics allow learners to construct, manipulate, and visualize geometric objects dynamically.

Researches have demonstrated that Geogebra-assisted lessons can enhance students' conceptual understanding, spatial visualization, and engagement compared to traditional approaches (Chimuka, 2024). More than cognitive outcomes, educational research increasingly emphasizes creativity and innovation as an essential tools for 21st-century skills, particularly relevant in resource-constrained environments. Mathematical creativity encompasses the generation of multiple, original and flexible solution strategies to non-routine problems, whereas innovation involves the application of disciplinary knowledge to generate contextually relevant and novel solutions.

Previous evidences of research links Geogebra-supported instruction to improved creative thinking and problem-based innovation in mathematics (Aliyu et al., 2022; Hassan et al., 2020). Despite these global findings, there is inadequate research on learners' perceptions of Geogebra impact on their capacity for creativity and innovation, especially among polytechnic students battling with economic hardship. In Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, where

institutional infrastructure are limited, and students' socio-economic circumstances are often challenging, understanding how students perceive the role of Geogebra can inform a sustainable, cost-effective instructional strategies that nurture entrepreneurial and design-oriented competencies in geometry and mathematics in general. Studies in Nigerian tertiary settings suggest that when ICT tools are available, learners respond positively in terms of motivation and willingness to explore, but perceptions tied to creative or innovative capacity remain under examined (Maccido et al., 2024; Umar et al., 2025 & ICT and learning of mathematics in Nigeria, 2022). Given the dual pressures of educational need and economic scarcity, investigating perceived impact of how students feel Geogebra shapes their creative and innovative thinking provides valuable insight. Such data can guide pedagogical decision-making, highlighted areas for professional development, and hypothetical institutional ICT strategy, even where budgets are tight. This study therefore find out the perceived impact of Geogebra technology on creativity and innovation in geometric learning in Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic.

Statement of the Problem

Geometry remains a critical component of polytechnic education, foundation skills in engineering design, construction, and applied sciences. However, in Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, many students face persistent difficulties in developing deep conceptual understanding and applying geometric principles creatively and innovatively. Traditional teaching methods, often dominated by lecture and static diagrams, limit opportunities for exploration, visualization, and problem-based learning. Economic hardship further composites these challenges by restricting access to modern learning resources, well-equipped laboratories, and supportive learning environments. In light of these, low-cost, open-source technological tools like Geogebra present an encouraging alternative for enhancing learning experiences. Research in

other part of the world has shown that Geogebra can foster creativity, innovation, and engagement in mathematics. Nonetheless, there is inadequate empirical evidences particularly in Umar Ali Shinkafi polytechnic Sokoto backgrounds about how students perceive its impact on their creative and innovative capacities in geometry. This study therefore seeks to investigate the perceived impact of Geogebra technology on the creativity and innovation of Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic students in geometric learning amidst ongoing economic hardship.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the perceived impact of Geogebra technology on Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic students' creativity and innovation in geometric learning amidst economic hardship. The specific objectives are:-

1. To examine students' perceptions of how Geogebra technology impacts their creativity in geometric learning.
2. To assess students' perceptions of how Geogebra technology impact their innovative problem-solving skills in geometry.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study

1. How do Umar Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic students perceive the impact of Geogebra technology on their creativity in geometric learning?
2. To what extent does the use of Geogebra technology impacts students' innovative approaches to solving geometry problems?

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was employed in the study as the design enabled the collection of data to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). It allows for representative sample of the population, thereby enhancing validity and capturing both measurable patterns and appropriate insights (Peters & Fábregues, 2024). The approach is particularly valuable in complex educational

settings influenced by socioeconomic constraints, aligning with the pragmatic paradigm of using “what works” in real-world settings (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The population of the study consisted of 20,214 students enrolled in the national diploma at Umar Ali Shinkafi polytechnic that offered courses leading to the award of national diploma. The population of the study was 660 participants in Mathematics related courses. The distribution of the target Population was presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Distribution of students’ targeted population across the programme in the Umar Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto.

S/N	Department	Students Population
1	Statistics & Computer Science	201
2	Engineering (Civil, Mechanical & Electrical)	172
3	Building Technology & Architecture	156
4	Quantity Surveying & Urban Planning	131
	Total	660

Source: (School website, 2025)

The sample of the study was selected using stratified sampling which, is a probability sampling techniques where by researchers divide a heterogeneous population into distinct non – corresponding subdivisions called strata base on a specific characteristic and reflect the populations’ diversity. A sample of 198 participants from the four (4) programme that offered courses leading to the award of national diploma was used as suggested by the research advisor software for the survey research design and obtained by stratified sampling technique. The sample was displayed in Table 2.

Table 2: The distributions of Students Sample across the programme in the Umar Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto

S/N	Department	Students Population
1	Statistics & Computer Science	60
2	Engineering (Civil, Mechanical & Electrical)	52

3	Building Technology & Architecture	47
4	Quantity Surveying & Urban Planning	39
	Total	198

Instrument for data collection

The instrument was Self-designed questionnaire and tagged as Perceived Impact of Geogebra on Creativity and Innovation (PIGCI) .It consisted of ten (10) items and had two sections of A and B. Section A of the instrument’s deals with the creativity in geometry learning using Geogebra, while Section B concerned with the innovation in geometry learning using Geogebra. In both Section A and B, the respondents are to tick the blanks where appropriate that best reveal his/ her opinion using four (4) points likert’s scale of 1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree. It was used for data collection.

Validity of the Instruments

The face and content validity of the PIGCI was determined by given it to 3 experts for judgments in the test and measurement, Psychology, Guidance and Counseling unit of guidance and counseling Department, Faculty of Education, Sokoto State University, Sokoto State, Nigeria. These experts were given copies of the instruments, topic of the study, aim and objectives and research questions as guide. Their observations were strictly used in the updated instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

The measure of internal consistency of the PIGCI was determined by administering it to 20 respondents in Federal Polytechnic Monguno, Borno State. The reason for choosing them is the fact that the respondents have similar characteristics in all respect with sample respondents and it was determined by the split-half method and subjected to Cronbatch’s Alpha formula, the value of 0.79 was obtained and considered good for used in the study.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed via Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24:0; Data was analyzed and used in answering research questions via descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation using the mean criterion of 2.5 and 1.12 obtained from four-point likert’s scale as criteria for accepting or rejecting

The data collected was analyzed by the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24:0; Data was analyzed based on research questions. in which, research questions were answered by descriptive mean and standard deviation through using the mean and standard deviation criterion of 2.5 and 1.12 obtained from four points likert’s scale as criteria for accepting or rejecting.

Results

Table 3: Perceived impact of Geogebra technology on Umar Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic students’ creativity in learning

No.	STATEMENT	S.A (4)	A (3)	D (2)	S.D(1)	MEAN (X)	STD	DECISION
c ₁	Using Geogebra helps me generate many different ideas for solving geometry problems.	96	58	25	19	3.18	1.16	Accepted
c ₂	I can approach geometry problems from multiple perspectives when using Geogebra.	82	78	12	26	3.09	1.13	Accepted
c ₃	Geogebra encourages me to develop unique or unusual solutions in geometry.	112	38	16	32	3.16	1.15	Accepted
c ₄	I can refine and improve my geometry solutions more effectively when using Geogebra.	95	85	11	7	3.35	1.31	Accepted
c ₅	Geogebra makes me more confident in experimenting with various strategies in geometry.	104	88	4	2	3.48	1.48	Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the Perceived impact of Geogebra technology on Umar Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic students’ creativity in geometric learning, as respondents said using Geogebra helps them generate many different ideas for solving geometry problems as the mean and standard deviation are 3.18 and 1.16. Furthermore, the result also point out that they can approach geometry problems from multiple perspectives when using Geogebra, Geogebra encourages them to develop unique or unusual solutions in geometry, they can refine and improve their geometry solutions

more effectively when using Geogebra and Geogebra makes me more confident to experiment with various strategies in geometry respectively with 3.09 and 1.13, 3.16 and 1.15, 3.35 and 1.31 and 3.48 and 1.48 of mean and standard deviation scores. The overall overview of data in table, revealed that majority respondents perceived that there was a high impact of Geogebra technology on the students’ creativity in geometric learning which was higher than the mean and standard deviation criterion of 2.5 and 1.12 obtained from four-point likert’s scale.

Table 4: Extent to which the use of Geogebra technology impacts students’ innovative approaches to solving geometry problems

S/N	STATEMENT	SA(4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD(1)	MEAN	SD	DECISION
I ₁	I often discover new methods for solving geometry problems through Geogebra.	69	112	15	2	3.25	1.23	Accepted
I ₂	Geogebra motivates me to try out untested ideas in my geometry work.	115	62	14	7	3.44	1.41	Accepted

I ₃	I use Geogebra to create original geometric designs or models that i have not seen before.	96	70	12	20	3.22	1.21	Accepted
I ₄	Geogebra helps me adapt existing geometry methods to develop better solutions.	122	38	20	18	3.33	1.34	Accepted
I ₅	I can present my geometry solutions in more creative and engaging ways because of Geogebra.	110	54	18	16	3.30	1.31	Accepted

Result from table 4 above show the extent to which the use of Geogebra technology impacts students’ innovative approaches to solving geometry problems. The respondents point out that they often discover new methods for solving geometry problems through Geogebra as the mean and standard deviation are 3.25 and 1.23 respectively. Additionally, the respondents point out that, Geogebra motivates them to try out untested ideas in their geometry work, they use Geogebra to create original geometric designs or models that they have not seen before, Geogebra helps them to adapt existing geometry methods to develop better solutions and with 3.25 and 1.23; 3.44 and 1.41; 3.22 and 1.21; 3.33 and 1.34 and 3.30 and 1.31 mean and standard deviation scores respectively which was greater than mean criterion of 2.5 and 1.12 obtained from four point likert’s scale.

Discussion

From the analyzed data, the results from Tables 3 and 4 show that Geogebra significantly enhances students’ creativity and innovation in geometric learning, with all mean scores (3.09–3.48 for creativity; 3.22–3.44 for innovation) surpassing the criterion mean of 2.5. Students reported that Geogebra enables them to generate diverse ideas, approach problems from multiple perspectives, refine solutions iteratively, and confidently experiment with new strategies indicating strong support for creativity. At the same time, they affirmed that the tool helps them discover new methods, try untested ideas, create original designs, and adapt existing methods into better solutions, reflecting high levels of innovation. These

findings align with Ahmad et al. (2023), who noted that Geogebra fosters innovative problem-solving, and Febrianti and Dasari (2024), who found that it strengthens creative thinking and originality in mathematics. Thus, the study establishes that Geogebra is not only creativity-enhancing but also an innovation enabler, offering a cost-effective solution for sustaining effective learning even amidst economic hardship.

Conclusion

This study concludes that Geogebra has a significant positive impact on Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic students’ creativity and innovation in geometric learning, as evidenced by their reports of generating diverse ideas, experimenting with untested strategies, refining solutions, and creating original designs, with all mean scores exceeding the criterion benchmark. These findings, consistent with Ahmad et al. (2023) and Febrianti and Dasari (2024), underscore Geogebra role as both a creativity enhancer and an innovation enabler in mathematics education. Importantly, its open-source and cost-free nature makes it particularly valuable in contexts of economic hardship, where access to quality resources is limited. The study therefore recommends integrating Geogebra into curricula, building teacher capacity, and supporting equitable access, positioning the technology as a sustainable and affordable pathway for advancing 21st-century skills in Nigerian higher education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Geogebra should be fully integrated into the teaching of geometry and related mathematics courses at polytechnic and university levels to strengthen students' creativity and innovation.
2. Professional development workshops and training sessions should be organized to equip lecturers with the skills to design and implement Geogebra-based learning activities effectively.
3. Educators should adopt inquiry-oriented approaches (e.g., problem-based learning and the 5E model) alongside Geogebra to maximize its impact on creative and innovative thinking.
4. Institutions should provide shared digital devices, offline Geogebra resources, and computer laboratory support to minimize gaps in access, especially amidst economic hardship.
5. Education policymakers should encourage the adoption of open-source technologies like Geogebra by allocating funds and resources to support their sustainable use in higher education.

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